

Macroeconomic stability factors of the USD/MAD exchange rate in the context of an open Moroccan economy

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Abstract:

This article aims to analyze the factors of the USD/MAD exchange rate in Morocco for the period from 1980 to 2018. We have used the ARDL model to verify the long-term stable relationship for a threshold of 1% between the USD/MAD exchange rate and its explanatory variables.

The results of our study show that in a long-term perspective, direct foreign investments, the money stock (M3), and the interest rate have a positive impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate, whereas the consumer price index, the exchange reserves, and the stock of external public debt have a negative impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate.

Keywords: ARDL, exchange rate, direct foreign investments, external public debt, interest rate.

1. Introduction

The early 1980s were marked by internal and external macroeconomic imbalances "trade balance deficit, unfavorable economic conditions, high oil prices, dependency of production on climatic variations". Morocco, under the auspices of the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, engaged in a stabilization and adjustment process to redress these internal and external imbalances. The reforms were implemented from 1983 to 1992. The structural adjustment program (SAP) produced negative impacts at a societal level (health, education...) and positive impacts at the macroeconomic level "increased foreign exchange reserves, improved debt ratios, moderate inflation"(DEPF, 1995). The Moroccan Dirham was linked to the French franc until May 1973. From that date, the Moroccan central bank implemented a fixed exchange rate regime. The objective was to stabilize the real exchange rate against a number of currencies related to Morocco's main trading partners. This fixation has the advantage of avoiding the risk of an excessive external debt burden when it's denominated in U.S. Dollars. This policy also has the advantage of limiting the effects of Dirham volatility on the trade balance and foreign direct investment (Rey et al., 2004). In 2004, the Moroccan central bank has implemented a reorganization of the currency basket, limiting its composition to Euro and U.S. Dollar with respective weights of 80% and 20%. These weights were revised in 2005 to 60% for Euro and 40% for U.S. dollars (BANK AL-MAGHRIB - Historique Du Régime de Change, n.d.).

The new exchange rate regime, which is more flexible, came into effect on January 15, 2018, with the widening of the fluctuation band from $\pm 2.5\%$ to $\pm 5\%$ in 2020. The exchange rate continued its evolution within the fluctuation band without the intervention of the central bank. The economic slowdown in 2020 had an impact on public finances, and the government amended the finance law by bringing measures to support businesses and households through grants from the special fund for pandemic management (Covid-19), which was created for that purpose. The budget deficit rose to 7.6% of GDP, public debt increased to 76.4% of GDP and the current account showed a deficit of 1.5% of GDP. Considering the external financing, official reserve assets increased (320.6 billion dirhams) representing 7.4 months of imports of goods and services (BANK AL-MAGHRIB - Rapport Annuel, 2020). According to the Moroccan central bank (2020 Report), the long-term success of the new and more flexible exchange rate regime is linked to the restoration of macroeconomic balances and the improvement of productivity. In fact, the long-term equilibrium exchange rate of developing countries is linked to internal and external

fundamentals. The selection of these fundamentals is a necessity to properly estimate the long-term equilibrium exchange rate. Developing countries with a low exchange rate misalignment are more competitive and a stable real exchange rate improves economic performance (Edwards, 1988). This paper attempts to provide some conclusions about the long-term equilibrium exchange rate in Morocco. We focus only on the USD/MAD exchange rate issue and its macroeconomic factors.

To better understand this topic, we present the theoretical framework of our study. Then, we study the determinants of the USD/MAD exchange rate by applying an ARDL model to annual data from 1980 to 2018. Finally, we present the results obtained and their discussion.

2. Theoretical framework

Table 1: key factors influencing exchange rate in the literature

Author (year)	Country and research period	Statistic method	Key factors influencing the exchange rate
Sunil et al. (2021)	India ; China (1995-2020)	Regression analysis	-GDP -consumer price index -interest rate -money supply
Oliinyk et al. (2020)	Ukraine (2006-2016)	Regression analysis	-GDP -inflation -interest rate -budget deficit -current account balance -financial account balance -export of goods and services -import of goods and services -gold and foreign exchange reserves -external debt stock - M2 money supply
Khan et al. (2019)	China (1980-2017)	ARDL	-GDP -inflation -annual interest rate -trade openness
Kilicarslan (2018)	Turkey (1975-2016)	GARCH	-foreign direct investments -gross fixed capital formation -trade openness -general government final consumption expenditure

Bourauoui & Phisuthtiwatcharavong, (2015)	Thailand (2004-2013)	Multiple linear regression	-public debt -differential interest rate -international reserves -monetary base -industrial production index -terms of trade
Chang & Su (2014)	Industrial countries (1986-2011)	VECM	-M1 money supply -industrial production index

Source: Developed by the authors

2.1. Exchange rate

Financial integration and monetary independence are among the advantages of a fully floating exchange rate. The export of similar products encourages developing countries to adopt "intermediate" solutions like an adjustable peg and fluctuating currency baskets (Braga de Macedo et al., 2001). According to Mundell (1963), a country cannot simultaneously implement the following three policies: free movement of capital, a fixed exchange rate, and an independent monetary policy. Countries exporting a similar range of products seek exchange rate stability and monetary independence (useful for managing economic recessions) and forgo financial integration. For example, Branson (2001) concluded that many developing countries, exporting similar products, control their floating exchange rate for fear of the instability of their foreign exchange market.

2.2. Consumer price index

Smith (1999) stated that the high inflation rate reduces exports by decreasing the demand for the country's currency in the international market. The depreciation of the country's currency is the consequence of a high general price level, which reduces exports and the exchange rate.

Khan et al. (2019) demonstrated through the ARDL approach that the inflation rate has a negative and significant effect on the USD/CNY exchange rate in China. An increase of 1% in the inflation rate caused a decrease of 0.62% in the USD/CNY exchange rate.

2.3. Foreign direct investments

Macroeconomic stability and a well-rated domestic market and stock exchanges are necessary conditions for foreign direct investment (Braga de Macedo et al., 2001). In a study on the exchange rate in Turkey, Kilicarslan (2018) demonstrated that foreign direct investment has a negative and significant impact on the volatility of the exchange rate.

2.4. Foreign exchange reserves

Foreign exchange reserves allow the central bank to have a stable exchange rate. In fact, foreign exchange reserves indicate the external balance situation of a country. If the transactions of an economy with the rest of the world are financed in an ordinary way and without using external financing, external stability is maintained. In some exchange rate theories, a country with a fixed exchange rate can accumulate high international reserves. On the other hand, a country with a floating exchange rate relies on the international market to defend the value of its currency. Foreign exchange reserves increase when the domestic currency is in high demand on the foreign exchange market, but they decrease when there is a higher supply of domestic currency on the foreign exchange market. M. T. Khan (2013) showed that nominal and real exchange rates have an impact on foreign exchange reserves in Pakistan. Bouraoui & Phisuthtiwatcharavong (2015) concluded that foreign reserves have a positive and significant impact on the THB/USD exchange rate in Thailand.

2.5. Money stock

Oliinyk et al. (2020) have shown that exchange rate and money supply have a positive and significant long-term relationship. Money supply and exchange rate have an equilibrium relationship in the long term. Money stock has a positive and significant impact on the THB/USD exchange rate in Thailand (Bouraoui & Phisuthtiwatcharavong, 2015; Chang & Su, 2014).

2.6. Interest rate

The high-interest rate in the economy causes domestic inflation, which depreciates the value of money (Jaffe & Mandelker, 1976). The interest rate has a negative and significant effect on the exchange rate (Abbas Qaisar et al., 2012).

M. K. Khan et al. (2019) have shown that the decrease in value of the USD/CNY exchange rate is due to the increase in the interest rate of the domestic economy, a devaluation of 0.18% in the USD/CNY exchange rate is due to 1% increase in the interest rate. Wong (2013) demonstrated through the ARDL model that in the long term, the interest rate has a positive effect on the exchange rate in Malaysia.

2.7. External public debt

In developing countries, perfect capital mobility draws foreign exchange reserves. Liberalizing capital movements must take into account the constraint of a foreign currency debt. The experience shows that many payers have adopted an intermediate exchange rate

regime because of the external debt constraint (Branson, 2001). External public debt has a significant impact on the exchange rate. Bouraoui & Phisutthiwatcharavong (2015), concluded that public debt is the main determining factor of the THB/USD exchange rate, the authors added that the production of technology is an important variable to determine the effect of public debt on the exchange rate in the long run.

3. Methodological framework

The provided literature review allows us to identify the different channels through which the exchange rate can be impacted by specific explanatory factors. In this section, we first specify the econometric model and the source of the used variables, and then we present the econometric estimation method.

3.1. Model specification and data source

This study took into account some variables suggested by economic theory, or tested in other countries, especially developing ones.

The model specification is as follows:

$$Tx_{ch} = f(IDE, IPC, MM, Tr, Std, Tx_i)$$

Table 2: Description of the used variables

Variables	Description	Expected effect
Explanatory variables		
<i>Std</i>	The stock of external public debt	(-)
<i>IDE</i>	Foreign direct investment	(+)
<i>IPC</i>	Consumer price index	(-)
<i>MM</i>	Money supply (M3)	(+)
<i>Tr</i>	Total reserves	(-)
<i>Tx_i</i>	The interest rate	(+)
Explained variable		
<i>Tx_{ch}</i>	The USD/MAD exchange rate	

Source: Developed by the authors

The data used for the estimates are annual and cover the period from 1980 to 2018. They are obtained from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) database.

3.2. Estimation method

The "ARDL Bound Testing" approach was developed by Hashem Pesaran & Shin (1998); Pesaran et al. (2001), allows us to test the long-term relationships through bounds testing on series that are integrated of order (0) and (1) in order to obtain better estimates on smaller samples. We use this approach to study the explanatory factors of the USD/MAD exchange rate in Morocco.

The basic equation of the ARDL Bound Testing model is generally written as follows:

$$Y_t = a_0 + a_1Y_{t-1} + \dots + a_pY_{t-p} + \beta_0X_t + \beta_1X_{t-1} + \beta_2X_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_qX_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t$$

According to this equation, we can observe that the dependent variable is explained by the explanatory variable as well as by its lags and the delays in the exogenous variables. Assuming that there are two explanatory variables used in the modeling in addition to the dependent variable, the model is as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p a_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \gamma_i \Delta X_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_i \Delta X_{2t-i} + \theta ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

With:

ECT is the speed of adjustment to equilibrium in the long run and θ represents the error correction coefficient.

We replace the speed of adjustment to equilibrium by $Y_{(t-i)}$, $X_{(1t-i)}$, and $X_{(2t-i)}$. The new model becomes:

$$\Delta Y_t = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p a_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \gamma_i \Delta X_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_i \Delta X_{2t-i} + \theta_0 Y_{t-1} + \theta_1 X_{1t-1} + \theta_2 X_{2t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

This equation is attributed to an error correction model, as Pesaran, Shin & Smith (2001) mentioned. It allows us to jointly model the short-term dynamics, represented by the variables in the first difference, and the long-term dynamics represented by the level variables. The ARDL modeling allows to consider the problem of multicollinearity between the explanatory variables.

Adopting the "ARDL Bound Testing" approach, the model to be estimated is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Tx_ch = & a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p a_{1i}Tx_ch_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{2i}IDE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{3i}IPC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{4i}MM_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{5i}Res_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{6i}Sdt_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q a_{7i}Tx_i_{t-i} + \theta_1Tx_ch_{t-1} \\ & + \theta_2IDE_{t-1} + \theta_3IPC_{t-1} + \theta_4MM_{t-1} + \theta_5Res_{t-1} + \theta_6Sdt_{t-1} + \theta_7Tx_i_{t-1} \\ & + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

With:

Δ : Differential operator;

P: Lag in the endogenous variable;

q: Maximum lag in the exogenous variables

a_p : Parameters of the long-term relationship

β_p : Parameters of the short-term relationship

4. Results and discussion

The first step of ARDL modeling is to test the stationarity of the considered variables. This step allows us to determine their order of integration, which must be between 0 and 1. To achieve this, we use the ADF unit root test.

Table 3: Results of the ADF unit root test

Variables	Specification	ADF	Critical values	Order of integration
Tx_ch	(At level)			
	M3	-0.339411	2.79	I(0)
	M2	4.268597	3.11***	
IPC	(At level)			
	M3	0.617009	2.79	I(0)
	M2	7.931040	3.11***	
IDE	(At level)			I(1)
	M3	4.679490	2.79	
	M2	1.869774	3.11	
	M1	-0.537304	2.54	
	(In 1st d)			
	M3	-0.194885	2.79	
M2	0.564829	3.11		
M1	-15.17779	2.54***		
MM	(At level)			I(1)
	M3	1.783234	2.79	
	M2	1.623964	3.11	
	M1	3.942882	2.54	
	(In 1st d)			

	M3	-0.157546	2,79	
	M2	1.869354	3,11	
	M1	-1.770510	2,54*	
Tr	(At level)			I(1)
	M3	1.740622	2,79	
	M2	1.594332	3,11	
	M1	-0.882014	2,54	
	(In 1st d)			
	M3	-0.647108	2,79	
Std	M2	0.399743	3,11	I(1)
	M1	-2.792707	2,54***	
	(At level)			
	M3	-2.873180	2,79	
	M2	0.791632	3,11	
	M1	-0.417718	2,54	
Tx_i	(In 1st d)			I(1)
	M3	-0.197882	2,79	
	M2	-0.967421	3,11	
	M1	-2.769216	2,54***	
	(At level)			
	M3	-2.348849	2,79	
Tx_i	M2	0.464412	3,11	I(1)
	M1	-1.039492	2,54	
	(In 1st d)			
	M3	-0.619713	2,79	
	M2	-0.835445	3,11	
	M1	-4.174085	2,54***	
The selection of the right model for this test is made based on the ADF test strategy. The number of lags selected to perform the test is given automatically by EViews 12. The critical values are the values tabulated by McKinnon (1996) at the 5% and 10% threshold.				

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

The results shown in Table 3 confirm the existence of variables that are integrated of the same order (I(1)), while the exchange rate and consumer price index variables are stationary at level (I(0)). These results imply the fulfilment of the first condition of the ARDL model. Thus, the analysis of the cointegration between the exchange rate and the explanatory variables is an essential condition in ARDL modeling. This approach verifies the existence of long-term dynamics in the equation linked to the variation of the USD/MAD exchange rate.

To test the existence of a cointegration between series, the econometric literature suggests several tests or approaches including the cointegration test of Pesaran et al. (2001), which

has been used as an analytical tool when there is a set of variables with a different order of integration.

The Pesaran & Shin (2001) test is expressed as follows: the hypothesis of the existence of a cointegrating relationship (H0) is accepted if the calculated Fisher is greater than the critical upper bound value.

The cointegration analysis requires at first the determination of the optimal number of lags. We will use the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to select the optimal ARDL model, which provides statistically significant results with the least number of parameters. Below are the estimation results of the selected optimal ARDL model.

Figure 1: Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

The following table summarizes the lags of our optimal model:

Table 4 : Optimal lag number

Variables	Tx_ch	IDE	IPC	MM	Tr	Std	Tx_i
Optimal	p	q1	q2	q3	q4	q5	q6
lag number	1	0	3	2	3	3	3

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

Based on the results obtained, the ARDL model (1, 0, 3, 2, 3, 3, 3) is the most optimal among the 19 others presented. Moreover, the following tests show at first that there is no autocorrelation of errors nor heteroscedasticity, and also the errors are normal. Therefore,

the estimation of the above model is well specified because the P-values associated with the tests are higher than 5%.

Table 5: Tests of the stochastic assumptions' violation of the ARDL model

Hypothesis	Test	Statistic	P-value
Autocorrelation	Breusch-Godfrey	12.66	0.2054
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	23.34	0.3258
Normality	Jarque-Bera	0.26	0.8775

Source: Developed by the authors / Eviews 12 software

After estimating the ARDL model, we can perform the bounds cointegration test of Pesaran. The calculated test statistic, Fisher's F-value, will be compared to the critical values. The following table provides the results of the Pesaran cointegration.

Table 6: Results of the cointegration test of Pesaran

	Value	
Fcalculated	4.306	
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

The results of the cointegration test confirm the existence of a cointegrating relationship between the studied series (the value of F-stat=4.306 is > that of the upper bound (3.61) at the 5% threshold), which allows us to estimate the long-term relationship between the USD/MAD exchange rate and its explanatory factors. After detecting the cointegration relationship between the studied variables, we estimate the parameters of the ARDL econometric model in the short and long term.

Table 7: Estimation of the long-term parameters

Variable to be explained: USD/MAD exchange rate				
Explanatory variables	Coefficient	Standard deviation	t-statistic	P-value
IDE	0.246081	0.089307	2.755434	0.0096***
IPC	-0.136080	0.013802	-9.859531	0.0000***
MM	0.085422	0.013675	6.246667	0.0000***
Tr	-0.015568	0.005363	-2.902866	0.0066***
Std	-0.076493	0.010316	-7.415324	0.0000***
Tx_i	0.463644	0.138614	3.344861	0.0021***
C	1.886208	1.066639	1.768366	0.0865*

*, ** and *** indicate significant levels at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

Table 8: Estimation of the short-term parameters

Variable to be explained: USD/MAD exchange rate				
Explanatory variables	Coefficient	Standard deviation	t-statistic	P-value
Tx_ch(-1)	0.468588	0.182120	2.572968	0.0221**
IDE	-0.019020	0.130958	-0.145237	0.8866
IPC	-0.241070	0.115197	-2.092679	0.0551**
IPC(-1)	0.144349	0.141501	1.020130	0.3250
IPC(-2)	0.225686	0.130884	1.724319	0.1066
IPC(-3)	-0.124178	0.088584	-1.401814	0.1828
MM	0.027350	0.044614	0.613037	0.5497
MM(-1)	0.063581	0.045854	1.386604	0.1872
MM(-2)	-0.063207	0.036416	-1.735715	0.1046
Tr	0.028810	0.014108	2.042093	0.0605*
Tr(-1)	-0.029395	0.026203	-1.121836	0.2808
Tr(-2)	0.017817	0.027172	0.655717	0.5226
Tr(-3)	-0.022125	0.017879	-1.237477	0.2363
Std	0.063693	0.024368	2.613810	0.0204**
Std(-1)	-0.011757	0.021584	-0.544708	0.5945
Std(-2)	-0.006250	0.020964	-0.298158	0.7700
Std(-3)	-0.043350	0.020098	-2.156953	0.0489**
Tx_i	0.214127	0.287251	0.745435	0.4683
Tx_i(-1)	-0.058970	0.406018	-0.145239	0.8866
Tx_i(-2)	-0.477028	0.391638	-1.218032	0.2433
Tx_i(-3)	0.878932	0.263270	3.338526	0.0049***
C	-0.541065	1.965117	-0.275335	0.7871
CointEq(-1)	-0.753919	0.182120	-4.139696	0.0010***

*, ** and *** indicate significant levels at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

Table 7 shows the long-term results of the ARDL model. We used the USD/MAD exchange rate as the explained variable and the direct foreign investment, consumer price index, money supply (M3), foreign exchange reserves, stock of external public debt, and interest rate as explanatory variables.

The results of the ARDL model indicate that direct foreign investment has a positive and significant impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate. The coefficient indicates that a 1% increase in direct foreign investment appreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate by 0.246%. This result is in contrast with Kilicarslan (2018). Where direct foreign investment in Turkey has a negative and significant impact on exchange rate. The demand for Moroccan Dirham in the foreign exchange market for investment purposes has a positive impact on the appreciation of the USD/MAD exchange rate in the long-term.

In the long run, the consumer price index has a negative and significant impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate. An increase of 1% in the general price level causes a 0.136% depreciation of the USD/MAD exchange rate, which is consistent with the results of M. K. Khan et al. (2019) who found that the USD/CNY exchange rate depreciates by 0.62% following a 1% increase of inflation in China.

Morocco's exports have a low added value and an increased competition in the international market. According to Smith (1999), low-value-added products are sensitive to domestic inflation in the international market. Any increase in the general price level reduces the level of Moroccan exports, which depreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate.

In the long term, the money supply (M3) has a positive and significant impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate. Indeed, a 1% increase in M3 money supply appreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate by 0.085%. This result is consistent with that of Sunil et al.(2021), who demonstrated by regression analysis that money supply and exchange rate have a positive and significant relationship in the long term.

In the long term, foreign exchange reserves in Morocco have a negative and significant impact on exchange rate. A 1% increase in foreign exchange reserves depreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate by 0.015%. This result is contradictory to that of Bouraoui & Phisutthiwatcharavong (2015); M. T. Khan (2013) who concluded that foreign exchange reserves have a positive and significant impact on exchange rate. Exports in Morocco cover only 62% of imports (Office des changes, 2020), thus imports negatively affect foreign exchange reserves which depreciates the exchange rate. Foreign exchange reserves in Morocco are the product of financing mobilized by the Treasury. "The authorities have drawn on the precautionary and liquidity line of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) an amount of approximately 3 billion dollars. Taking into account the external financing mobilized by the Treasury, the official reserve assets of Bank AL-Maghreb have increased to 320.6 billion dirhams, representing a coverage of 7.4 months of goods and services' imports..."(*BANK AL-MAGHRIB - Rapport Annuel 2020*, n.d.).

In the long term, the stock of external public debt has a negative and significant impact on the USD/MAD exchange rate. An increase of 1% in the stock of Moroccan external public debt depreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate by 0.076%. This result confirms that of (Bouraoui & Phisutthiwatcharavong (2015), where public debt has a negative effect on the THB/USD exchange rate in Thailand. External public debt in developing countries like Morocco is the result of a deficit in the trade balances and a low attraction for direct foreign investment. These

results are contradictory to those of Hsing Yu (2015), who concluded that public debt is the main determining factor of the USD/PLN exchange rate.

In the long term, the coefficient of interest rate is positive and significant because a 1% increase in interest rate appreciates the USD/MAD exchange rate by 0.463%. This result confirms that of Wong (2013), who concluded that the interest rate in Malaysia positively affects the exchange rate. While other studies have concluded that the interest rate has a negative impact on exchange rate (Bouraoui & Phisutthiwatcharavong, 2015). A stable system is characterized by the use of interest rate to rebalance the deficit in the trade balance by increasing interest rate and attracting direct foreign investment (Mundell, 1963).

Table 8 confirms the long-term equilibrium relationship between the explanatory variables and the USD/MAD exchange rate. The coefficient of adjustment towards equilibrium [CointEq (-1)] is statistically significant and negative. In other words, it is the parameter that adjusts the shocks of the USD/MAD exchange rate variable. Following a shock, the exchange rate response variable returns to equilibrium with a frequency of 75.39%. The shock is fully resolved after one year and three months ($1/0.75=1.33$).

In the short term, the coefficients of the explanatory variables are not significant. The macroeconomic variables only explain the exchange rate in the long term. "The volatility of the exchange rate in the short term is explained by international finance. Macroeconomic fundamentals are irrelevant to exchange rate volatility" (Flood et al., 1999).

Figure 2: Structural stability of the estimators

Source: Developed by the authors / EViews 12 software

Statistically, we note that the CUSUM statistic of the recursive residuals lies within the critical values of the interval defined by the two parallel lines. This means that the estimators are stable, and consequently, there is no structural change during the study period

5. Conclusions and recommendations

In this paper, we examined the long-term relationship between the USD/MAD exchange rate and its explanatory factors. Based on the results of our study, the interest rate is the appropriate instrument for rebalancing the trade balance deficit and for attracting direct foreign investment (Mundell, 1963).

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